

The Big Bang as a Holographic Projection in QIH

A Field of Black Holes Composing Reality

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), the concept of a field of black holes composing reality provides a profound explanation for why the Big Bang seems to emerge from every point in space. This framework suggests that spacetime itself is a holographic projection arising from the interference patterns of countless microscopic black holes, each encoding information through their event horizons.

The Perception of the Big Bang from Every Point

The perception that the Big Bang originates from every point in space is a natural outcome of this holographic field. When viewed through the lens of QIH, each Planck-scale black hole contributes its quantum state to the global structure of spacetime, much like pixels on a screen collectively form an image. These black holes aren't just isolated objects; they form a dense, interconnected field, creating a continuous fabric where every point holds encoded information about the entire universe.

Isotropy and Homogeneity Explained

This perspective also aligns with the observation that the universe appears isotropic and homogeneous at large scales. The holographic projection from these black holes distributes the encoded quantum information uniformly across the event horizons, creating a seamless field of reality. As a result, when we look back in time toward the Big Bang, the initial singularity doesn't appear as a single point but as an all-encompassing projection—an event that seems to emerge simultaneously from every point in space.

The Role of Quantum State Vectors and Interference Patterns

The entangled quantum state vectors (QSVs) of this black hole field spin and interact, creating interference patterns that define spacetime curvature, probability, and the dynamics of the universe. These patterns also encode the inflationary expansion of the universe, explaining how the Big Bang's energy and information propagate outward in a holographic manner.

The Universe as a Unified Holographic Field

In essence, the idea that the Big Bang comes from every point is a direct result of the field of black holes composing reality. Each black hole, through its event horizon, participates in the creation of the universe as a holographic projection. This not only unifies the microscopic and macroscopic scales but also provides a deeply connected view of the universe, where every point contains the encoded history of the cosmos.

The holographic principle states that the information within a volume of spacetime is encoded on its boundary, such as the event horizon of a black hole. The entropy S of the black hole is proportional to the surface area A of its event horizon rather than the volume:

$$S = \frac{4G\hbar k_B c^3}{16\pi} A.$$

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), spacetime itself is treated as a lattice of Planck-scale black holes. Each black hole contributes its entropy, encoded as quantum information on its event horizon. These event horizons collectively form a holographic screen, which projects the interference patterns originating from the singularity.

Hawking radiation connects the quantum mechanical properties of black holes to their thermodynamic characteristics. The energy of each quantum of Hawking radiation is given by:

$$E = \hbar\omega,$$

where ω is the angular frequency of the emitted radiation. The total energy emitted by a black hole relates to its mass M via:

$$E = Mc^2.$$

Substituting, we find:

$$\hbar\omega = Mc^2,$$

indicating that the angular frequency of the Hawking radiation serves as the projection operator, mapping the internal quantum states of the singularity onto the event horizon. The interference patterns on the event horizon encode the dynamics and geometry of spacetime, analogous to watching a movie projected through a mirror.

Let the quantum states inside the singularity be represented by a wavefunction $\psi(\vec{x}, t)$, where $\vec{x}$ is a position vector in the bulk.

The holographic projection operator maps these states onto the event horizon, parameterized by spherical coordinates (θ, ϕ) on the Bloch sphere. Mathematically:

$$\Psi_{\text{horizon}}(\theta, \phi) = \int \psi(\vec{x}, t) e^{i\omega t} d^3x,$$

where $e^{i\omega t}$ encodes the angular frequency of Hawking radiation, and the integration represents the projection onto the two-dimensional surface.

The event horizon's interference patterns arise from the constructive and destructive interference of Quantum State Vectors (QSVs) encoded on Planck-scale qubits. Let the QSV of

a qubit be $|\psi\rangle = \cos(\theta/2)|0\rangle + e^{i\phi}\sin(\theta/2)|1\rangle$. The combined state of neighboring qubits forms the holographic interference pattern:

$$\Psi_{\text{total}} = \prod_i [\cos(\theta/2)|0\rangle_i + e^{i\phi}\sin(\theta/2)|1\rangle_i].$$

The resulting pattern encodes curvature, probability density, and quantum entanglement.

The Big Bang appears to originate from every point because the holographic screen encodes a uniform field of quantum information projected from the singularity. The uniformity of the cosmic microwave background (CMB) supports this, as the field of Planck-scale black holes distributes quantum information isotropically.

The holographic nature ensures that the total interference pattern represents the sum-over-histories of all possible quantum states. The Feynman path integral formalism demonstrates this:

$$\Psi(\vec{x}, t) = \int e^{iS[x(t)]/\hbar} D[x(t)],$$

where $S[x(t)]$ is the action along a path $x(t)$, and the summation includes contributions from all possible paths. The event horizon encodes these probabilities as interference patterns:

$$P(\theta, \phi) = |\Psi_{\text{horizon}}(\theta, \phi)|^2.$$

Thus, the observable universe emerges as the sum of all possible quantum histories projected onto the holographic screen.

In QIH, spacetime is composed of a dense field of black holes. Each black hole contributes its quantum state, creating a continuous holographic field. The metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, describing spacetime curvature, emerges from the collective entanglement of QSVs:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} = c^4 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}.$$

Here, $T_{\mu\nu}$ is derived from the encoded information and energy-momentum of the black hole field. The apparent isotropy and homogeneity of the Big Bang are a direct consequence of the uniform distribution of quantum states across this field.

The projection of interference patterns from the singularity onto the event horizon explains why the Big Bang seems to emerge from every point. The angular frequency of Hawking radiation acts as the projection operator, encoding quantum information on the holographic screen. This information forms the fabric of spacetime, with its curvature and dynamics emerging from the collective interactions of Planck-scale black holes. Thus, QIH provides a mathematically consistent and conceptually elegant framework for understanding the universe's holographic origins.